

EFFECTS OF CUMULATIVE PRACTICE ON STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICAL GEOMETRICAL CONSTRUCTIONS IN ANKPA L.G.A. OF KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study investigated the effect of cumulative practice approach on SS one students' achievement in mathematical geometrical construction in Ankpa Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria. The study employed a pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental control group design. Four intact classes, one each from each of the four schools setting were used. The sample for the study consisted of 204 SSS1 students. The instrument used for this study was the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), with reliability coefficient of 0.77. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that students who were taught using cumulative practice approach achieved higher than those that were taught using conventional practice approach. The study recommended among others, workshops/seminars for teachers to enable students acquire the basic skills of the cumulative practice approach. Curriculum planners and publishers should make efforts of providing text books or computer assisted materials in mathematics that conform with cumulative practice approach.

Keywords: cumulative practice, students' achievement, geometrical constructions

1. Introduction

Mathematics is a systematized and organized branch of science: which is basically concerned with ideas, processes and reasoning, all of which aim at solving problem. It

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is the study of patterns and relationships. (Odili, 2006; Grady, 2012). Mathematics is embedded in all human activities, thus, no amount of time and energy directed towards making learners acquire in-depth mathematical knowledge and requisite application can be too much. A common man can get on very well in life without learning how to read and write, but not without learning how to count and calculate. Any person ignorant of mathematics will be at the mercy of others and can easily be cheated. The fundamental processes and skills to use them remain basic to human beings these days (Sidhu, 2006).

Every subject needs mathematics, the queen and servant of all subjects for its foundation (Kurumeh, 2007). Since no profession/career is devoid of mathematics, and all subjects have mathematics as their foundation, it means mathematics achievement is very important and a major factor in students' career development. Odili (2006) posits that mathematics without any doubt remains the most serviceable science subject to all discipline and fields of human work and study. Mathematics is the language used in science and technology. Technology is the application of the principles derived from science and knowledge to the benefit of mankind. All theoretical findings can only be made beneficial when it is translated to reality through construction, thus the choice of construction aspect of mathematics for the study.

Students' poor performance (under achievement) in mathematics is a worldwide issue and not peculiar to Nigeria alone (Banerjee, 2016). Poor (low) performance of secondary school students in mathematics has remained a source of worry of many studies (Ezema, 2000). The annual Chief Examiner's report (CER) of West African Senior School Certificate Examination confirms the poor (low) performance (CER, 2012, 2013, 2014 & 2015). The different ways of how to improve the teaching and learning of mathematics with the hope of it leading to improved performance of students in mathematics has been the concern of many mathematics educators and researchers. These efforts are made in realization of the importance of the place (position) of mathematics in the scientific and technological growth and development of any nation. For Nigeria to achieve the vision 20-2020, a lot has to be done in the area of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education (STME) (Eriba and Iyekekpolo, 2006). The needed scientific and advancement technologically, can only be achieved with an initial and continuous improvement on the mathematics achievement of students (citizenry).

The chief examiner's report (CER) (WASSCE, 2014), asserts that candidates performed poorly in some questions. The chief examiner identify Inability to recall or lack of knowledge of the basic principles needed to tackle some of the problems, as candidates abandoned some problems half way as a result of confusion as to the correct concept or rule to be used (Banerjee, 2016; Gorgievski, 2011). These could be as a result of inadequate practice. (CER, 2014, 2015)

Construction is one of the topics in senior secondary school mathematics syllabus. In most years, there is usually a full question in the theory paper of both WASSCE and NECO devoted to construction. The report of chief examiners shows that most students do not attempt the questions and those that do, attempt poorly. The topic is very important for it is a way of putting into reality the theoretical aspects of

mathematics. It is through construction that the discoveries made theoretical can be put into the benefit of enhancing and comforting the life of the citizenry. Making life more comfortable is a major aim of education. Another issue is that construction helps in no small measure to demystify mathematics. If we are to produce good engineers, it is no gain saying that the educational sector of the secondary level should be able to lay a good foundation on the students' knowledge on construction.

As a remedy to avert the continuous annual poor performance of candidates in mathematics and the above identified topics in particular, the Chief Examiner suggests that constructions should be well taught in schools. The Chief Examiner suggests rekindling of students' interest through cumulative practice (CER, 2014). Based on the above suggestion the study was conducted to ascertain the possible effect cumulative practice approach could have on students' achievement in construction.

Many methods and strategies have been developed over several years. Among these methods are Ethnomathematics approach, Cuisenaire rods' approach, Cooperative learning approach, Delayed-Formalization approach, and others, all aimed at arousing and sustaining student's enthusiasm and improve achievement in mathematics. The hope is to have students use acquired mathematical skills to solve practical problems.

Mathematics is a spiral subject. Often the knowledge of many concepts is required in the process of solving some problem (Grady, 2012). The Chief Examiner's report WASSCE (2012), opines that each topic in Mathematics is not isolated. It is common to see many students starting the solution to some problems and get stocked for not knowing or forgetting the next concept to apply (Banerjee, 2016). The cumulative practice approach is aimed at making students practice skills learnt at regular interval. This is to make them to recall easily the skill whenever it is needed in solving a problem.

The conventional practice currently in use in mathematics education for many years is that of having student practice only on the immediate past concept learnt. The effect of this type of practice on students' achievement seems not noticeable as performance remains low year after year. Cumulative practice is just like as coaches and music teachers take complicated activity and break it into sub-skills until the sub-skills are mastered. Cumulative practice approach begins by independently training skills to mastery and then practicing it. Another skill is then trained to mastery and practice together, by mixing tasks for both skills within the same practice set. (Carnine, 1997; Park and Leung, 2003; Gorgievski, 2011). If there are N different concepts, each concept is repeatedly practiced $(N + 1 - P)$ times where P is the ordinal position of the concept ($P = 1, 2, \dots, N$). The first concept is practiced N times, second concept $(N - 1)$ times, third concept $(N - 2)$ times and so on. The review/assignment questions for each rule vary slightly at each review period. The number of review/assignment questions per rule reduces gradually as the number of rules to be reviewed increases in each review sessions.

Following the remarkable performance of Korean students in international competitive examinations Park and Leung (2003) investigated the process of learning.

They found that the process of learning often starts with gaining competence in the procedure, and then through cumulative practice students gradually gain understanding. Leung (2001) reports that in the East Asian lessons, a set of practicing exercises that vary systematically are highly used. The process thus make cumulative practice becomes an important route to understanding. These studies were done in other countries other than Nigeria. This study determined if the findings in Nigeria and Yagba East local government area of Kogi State in particular perhaps could be the same or differ. Construction is hierarchical and perhaps could be taught using cumulative practice approach. This could help students to connect new idea or concept to the previous one.

The purpose of education is to enable learner construct knowledge rather than commit knowledge to memory (Grady, 2012). Effective mathematics teaching requires a serious commitment to the development of students' understanding of mathematics, as students learn by connecting new ideas to prior knowledge (Grady, 2012).

There is a basic need for a learner to acquire the basic skills before one can talk of the application. The cumulative practice approach is meant to let the students' have intensive distributed practice on many related rules or concepts. This is necessary as mathematics is a highly structured subject because whatever is learnt at a higher level is dependent on what is learnt at the lower level (Kurumeh, 2009).

Skinner's operant conditioning and Thorndike's law of exercise constitute the theoretical framework this study adopted. Thorndike among many other laws formulated the law of exercise. Thorndike explained that repetition promotes learned association (stimulus and response). Constant practice is necessary if an action is to be strengthened. Lack of practice may weaken it (Alao and Adeniyi, 2009; Pane, Steiner, Mathew, Hamilton, & Pane, 2017). This study thus intend to determine what effect cumulative practice approach can have on the ability of senior secondary students to retain and retrieve easily the skills (concepts) involved in basic mathematical constructions operations.

2. Statement of the Problem

Poor performance of students in mathematics has persisted despite its importance. This has adverse effects on students' inability and denial to pursue their desired careers, and negative effect on the nation's desire for scientific and technological development (Tsue and Anyor, 2006).

West African Senior School Certificate Examination Chief Examiners' Report (CER 2014), has it that many candidates abandon solution to some problems half way as a result of confusion. Perhaps this could be as a result of inadequate practice. The statement *"I understand the mathematics when the teacher is teaching it in the classroom but forget it in examination hall"* is common among students/learners. One can deduce from the above statement that the method of teaching has actually passed the message across, but what is lacking is the ability to retain the knowledge and recall it when needed. The worry then is to find what can be done to make students' retain what they have learnt

longer and recall it when needed, thus the need to examine the effect of cumulative practice approach on senior secondary students' achievement in mathematical geometrical constructions.

2.1 Purpose of the Study

The study determined the effect of cumulative practice approach on Senior Secondary School Students' achievement in mathematical Geometrical constructions. in Ankpa Local Government Area of Kogi State. Specifically, the research aimed at: determining the effect of cumulative practice approach on senior secondary school students' achievement in mathematical constructions.

2.2 Research Question

To guide the study, the following research question was posed: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught with cumulative practice approach and those taught the same topics with the conventional methods?

2.3 Research Hypotheses

To further guide the study, the following null hypotheses was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught basic mathematical constructions using cumulative practice approach and the students taught the same topics with the conventional practice method.

2.5 Significance of the Study

A lot of studies have been done on various methods of teaching mathematics with most studies revealing better achievement tendencies among the students yet the final results in public examination is still below the desired level. It means there is still a problem, one of which is students' abandoning solution to a problem half way due to inability to recall the next concept or rule to apply (CER, 2013, 2014). There is therefore the need to go into finding the type of practice that could help the students/learner retain and recall concepts or rules easily in the course of finding solution to problems.

With an improved achievement (performance) of students in senior secondary mathematics, one major entry requirement to tertiary institutions in Nigeria is solved. An improved mathematics achievement will in no doubt have a positive effect on the science, technology and economic development of the nation. This will further enhance the possibility of attaining the vision 20-2020 of the nation, Nigeria. In effect students, parents, society and the government stands the chances of benefitting.

3. Methodology

The study employed a pre-test post test control group quasi-experimental design.

3.1 Population of Study

The target population of this study is all Senior Secondary School One Students (SSS I) in the 17 public secondary schools in Ankpa Local Government Area of Kogi State. These 17 schools have the total population of 1782 students in SSS1 (Kogi State Ministry of Education, Area Office, Ankpa, 2018).

3.2 Sample and Sampling

Four secondary schools, in Ankpa Local Government Area of Kogi State were used for the study. A total of two hundred and four students made up of one hundred and three and one hundred and one for the experimental and control groups respectively were used for the study.

Stratified random sampling technique was used. The schools in the study area were stratified into four groups based on distance between them, facilities and closeness of the experience of the mathematics teachers.

One school each was selected from each of the four groups using simple random sampling techniques (balloting). Two schools were assigned as experimental group and the other two as control group using simple random technique.

3.3 Research Instrument

Research instrument, Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), developed by the researchers and subjected to face validation by two (2) experts in mathematics education and one (1) expert in measurement and evaluation was used for data collection.

3.4 Reliability of the Research Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was carried out by subjecting it to two schools that were not among the schools used for the study. The reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained for MAT which indicates high degree and good for the study

3.5 Methodology

There was two days of three hours each day orientation for the research assistants who are the regular mathematics class teachers. The orientation programme covered the purpose of the research, the concepts to be taught, solving of the assignment questions and the mathematics achievement test and procedure for administering the instrument. The research assistants took their turns to lead in providing solution to the assignments and mathematics achievement test questions.

The mathematics achievement test (MAT) was administered before the commencement of the program by the research assistants. It was used to collect the pretest scores of both the experimental and control groups. The MAT was administered after the study (treatment) on both groups for the purpose of collecting the two groups posttest scores.

The trained regular class teachers did the teaching (experiment) in their respective schools, while the researcher monitored to ensure adherence to procedure.

Far distance between schools, orientation, used of regular class teachers and non-giving out of pretest scores were among methods used to control extraneous factors.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

The pretest scores of the experimental group and that of the control group were compared. This was to test for any significant difference in the mean pretest achievement scores of the groups. The analysis shows a significant level of 0.421 ($0.421 > 0.05$). This means there is no significant difference between the experimental and control groups before the treatment.

The researcher used mean and standard deviation of the data collected to answer the research questions. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze data in respect of the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

3.7 Research Question

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught using cumulative practice approach (experimental group) and those taught using the conventional approach (control group)?

Table 1: Results of Mean Achievement Scores of Experimental and Control groups

Group	N	Pretest mean	SD	Posttest mean	SD	Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
Experimental	103	3.77	2.040	13.43	3.650	9.66	5.15
Control	101	3.58	1.757	8.09	2.573	4.51	

Table 1 reveals that the subjects in both experimental and control groups were almost at same level of achievement in mathematical geometrical constructions before the commencement of the study, with mean pretest scores and standard deviations of (3.77;2.04) and (3.58;1.76) respectively. The experimental group had a mean posttest score of 13.43 with a standard deviation (SD) of 3.650 while the control group had a mean posttest score of 8.09 with a standard deviation of 2.573. The experimental group had mean gain of 9.66 while the control group had a mean gain of 4.51. The difference between the mean posttest scores of the two groups is 5.15 in favour of the experimental group. This means that the students in the experimental group taught mathematical geometrical construction using cumulative practice approach benefited more and therefore achieved higher than those in the control group taught using conventional approach.

3.7.1 Hypothesis (Ho₁)

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematical geometrical construction using cumulative practice approach and the students taught the same topics with the conventional practice method.

Table 2: Analysis of Co-variance among and in-between Experimental and Control groups

Source of Variation Corrected	Type III sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig	Remark
Model	1493.128(a)	8	186.641	18.368	.000	S
Intercept	4386.669	1	4386.669	431.719	.000	S
Pretest score	15.701	1	15.701	1.545	.215	NS
Group	1352.566	1	1352.566	133.114	.000	S
Error	1981.381	195	10.161			
Total corrected	27200.000	204				
Total	3474.510	203				

Table 2, reveals that cumulative practice approach has significant effect on students' mean achievement scores when taught mathematical geometrical construction using cumulative practice approach. Table 2 shows a calculated f value of 133.114 with $P=0.000$, with $P < 0.05$ it implies the mean gain difference of 5.15 in table 1 in favour of the students taught using cumulative practice approach is statistically significant. The null hypothesis is thus rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement score of students taught using cumulative practice approach and those taught using conventional approach on the posttest scores.

4. Discussion of Findings

Tables 1 and 2 show that students taught mathematical geometrical construction using cumulative practice approach achieved significantly higher than those taught using conventional approach. This may be because cumulative practice approach gives the greatest chance to truly cement concepts and to build upon what students have already learned. The more often students practices and builds upon skills, the more likely it is that they will master more aspects of the concepts and achieve more when the use of the concept to proffer solutions are required.

This finding is in line with the study carried out by Kristin and Philip (2002) on the effect of cumulative practice on students' achievement in mathematics. It is in line with the findings of Nguyen and Kulm (2005) in their study of using web-based practice to enhance mathematics learning and achievement on performing basic operations on fraction and decimals. The findings of Roundy and Roundy (2009) in their study of the effect of repeated reading on students' fluency: does practice always make perfect also confirm that students exposed to the repeated reading achieved higher.

The difference in mean achievement scores could be as a result of the fact that students taught using cumulative practice approach at each point of the review have the chance to discriminate or reinforce the skills learnt. It also affords the students to practice previously learnt rules they found difficult in another condition. Mastery of any skill requires ability to discriminate in procedures which cumulative practice can easily produce. Cumulative practice on each skill across a range of examples can ensure

generalization and extension (Skinner, 1957). The finding is supporting those of Kristin and Philip (2002), Nguyen and Kulm (2005) and Roundy and Roundy (2009).

4.1 Recommendations

The result of the study has shown that cumulative practice approach is an effective approach for improving students' mathematics achievement in mathematical geometrical construction. Based on this finding, effort should be made to popularize the use of cumulative practice approach in our secondary schools.

1. Workshops and seminars should be organized for serving teachers to enable them acquire the basic skills demanded by this approach.
2. Curriculum planners and mathematics teachers should make efforts at providing text book or computer assisted materials in mathematics that conforms with the cumulative practice approach. This is to offer teachers and students the opportunity of using the approach even when unguided.
3. Cumulative practice approach demands a lot of the time of the teachers as such they should be motivated to compensate for the extra job demand of the approach. The academic gain students will make from such approaches will justify the cost and extra demand of using it.

5. Conclusion

Results from the study showed that cumulative practice approach could lead to higher positive level of performance than the conventional approach. Cumulative practice approach could facilitate the learning of concepts that involve hierarchical and sequential set of skills of learning in mathematics. The cumulative practice approach has a positive effect on students' mathematics achievement.

It is hoped that teachers and students would avail themselves of the advantages of using cumulative practice approach so that the result that mathematics educators seek; performing well on component skills, extending the skills to a novel situation (application) and synthesizing the skills into novel solutions by combination of the skills (problem solving) can be achieved.

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